

Modern methods of diagnosis of digestive organs

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Conclusion. *Diseases of the digestive system are the most common among all diseases of internal organs. The "area of responsibility" of gastroenterology is the treatment of diseases of the esophagus, stomach, pancreas, intestines, gall bladder and liver. Digestion is a process of mechanical and chemical processing of food, as a result of which nutrients are absorbed and assimilated by the body, and decomposition products and undigested products are removed from it. Digestion is the first stage of metabolism. With food, a person receives energy and all the necessary substances for tissue regeneration and growth. However, proteins, fats and carbohydrates, as well as vitamins and mineral salts contained in food are foreign substances for the body and cannot be absorbed by its cells. These substances must first be converted into smaller molecules that are soluble in water and do not have specific properties. This process takes place in the digestive tract and is called digestion. The causes of indigestion are insufficient separation of gastric juice or a violation of the evacuation of contents due to a pathological process in any organ of the digestive system.*

Keywords: *colic or back pain, headache, irritability; dyspeptic diseases, nausea, vomiting, belching, palpitations*

Introduction. Manifestations of digestive disorders: loss of appetite, feeling of heaviness, wideness in the epigastric region, nausea, sometimes vomiting, diarrhea or constipation, bloating.

Symptoms of gastrointestinal diseases:

- a. colic or aching back pain, headache, irritability;
- b. dyspeptic diseases:
- c. nausea
- d. vomiting
- e. humming
- f. heartbeat
- g. loss of appetite
- h. unpleasant taste in the mouth
- i. holding the litter
- j. frequent loose stools
- k. flatulence
- l. jaundice.

Causes of gastrointestinal diseases

The modern rhythm of life, constant stress, poor nutrition, unfavorable environmental conditions - all this has a very negative effect on the condition of the human body, including the work of the gastrointestinal tract.

The number of people suffering from chronic gastroenterological diseases is increasing every year. And often the reason why the disease becomes chronic is self-medication.

You cannot heal yourself! It only worsens the course of the disease, and leads to only temporary improvement.

Dyspepsia

Dyspepsia is a general term for functional digestive disorders caused by inadequate digestion of digestive enzymes or poor nutrition.

Dyspepsia is characterized by:

- a. fermentation
- b. rotten
- c. oily

Fermentative dyspepsia is associated with excessive consumption of carbohydrates (sugar, honey, flour products, fruits, grapes, peas, beans, cabbage, etc.), as well as fermented drinks (kvass). As a result, conditions are created for the development of enzymatic flora in the intestines.

The cause of putrid dyspepsia is mainly the consumption of protein foods, especially lamb and pork, which are digested more slowly in the intestines. Sometimes rotten dyspepsia occurs as a result of eating stale meat products.

Fatty dyspepsia occurs as a result of excessive consumption of slow-digesting, especially refractory, fats (pork, lamb). Dyspepsia can accompany gastritis and pancreatitis.

Symptoms of dyspepsia

Fermentative dyspepsia - bloating, rumbling in the intestines, large amounts of gas; frequent, slightly colored, liquid, foamy stools with a sour smell.

Putrid dyspepsia - diarrhea with strong dark-colored stools and putrid odor. Against the background of general intoxication with rotten products, patients often complain of loss of appetite, weakness and decreased performance.

With fatty dyspepsia, stools are light, abundant and oily.

Treatment of dyspepsia

Drug therapy includes enzyme preparations.

The following drugs can be used as symptomatic treatment of dyspepsia: Almagel, Maalox and other acid-reducing agents; drugs that reduce gastric secretion - omeprazole, ranitidine, famotidine, etc.; enzyme preparations - acidinpepsin, abomin, pancreatin, etc.; prokinetics - motilium, etc.; drugs to restore microflora - bificol, colibacterin and a number of other groups.

Normalization of nutrition plays a very important role in the treatment of dyspepsia.

Fasting is usually prescribed for 1-1.5 days, then:

for rotten dyspepsia, it is necessary to increase the amount of carbohydrates in the daily diet

for enzymatic dyspepsia - proteins (at the same time reducing the amount of low molecular weight carbohydrates)

in the case of fatty dyspepsia, the body's intake of fats, especially fats of animal origin, is limited.

The main cause of dyspepsia must be identified and treated! All kinds of folk remedies can relieve the symptoms, but the cause of their occurrence cannot be removed! The disease appears again and again, and the disease that caused it goes to a chronic stage, in which treatment becomes more difficult or does not benefit at all.

In the treatment of gastrointestinal diseases, the alternative medicine center conducts an antiparasitic program and uses an inpatient/outpatient body cleansing program. The program is implemented to normalize the activity of the digestive tract, restore the liver, blood vessels, lymphatic system, restore metabolism and reduce body weight.

Program for restoring the functions of the gastrointestinal tract in an inpatient or outpatient setting: improving the motility of the large intestine (fighting constipation), restoring the microflora; improving the absorption of fats, proteins, carbohydrates, vitamins and trace elements in the small intestine; restoration of the secretory function of the stomach, pancreas, intestines; measures against

parasites; activate the gallbladder and liver to remove toxins from the body, normalize the properties of bile to break down fats

Examination: doctor's consultation, ultrasound examination of abdominal organs (liver, gall bladder, bile ducts, pancreas, spleen) and kidneys, EKG, virus, bacteria, parasites, vitamin and lack of micronutrients, food intolerance in the Medical Expertise Complex

Hypoallergenic diet: vegetarian, juice therapy, raw food diet

Therapeutic fasting for 10-15 days

Detoxification program: cleaning of large and small intestines, liver and gall bladder, kidneys, ozonated water, microclyses with ozonated oil, antiparasitic, choleric, kidney teas, massage

Sanitation of the large intestine with an ozone-oxygen mixture: increasing immunity, treating intestinal infections, removing mucus and parasites from the intestine, restoring microflora

Sanitization of foci of chronic infections of ENT organs with ozone-oxygen mixture: effect on pathogenic microflora of ear, throat, nasal mucosa

Intravenous ozone therapy: anti-allergic, anti-inflammatory, detoxifying effect, cleansing blood and blood vessels of allergens and toxins, increasing immunity.

Antiparasitic program: correction of the condition of the body in the complex of medical experts, exposure to internal allergens (fungi, viruses, bacteria, worms, protozoa)

Pressotherapy: cleaning lymph from allergens and toxins, improving the drainage function of excretory organs.

Visceral massage: helps improve the drainage function of the intestinal lymphatic system, reduces intestinal spasms, clears mucus and parasites, increases immunity.

Duodenal intubation of the gallbladder: a method of removing bile from the gallbladder to improve the detoxification function of the liver and activate the immune system

Traction of the spine using the Ormed-Professional apparatus: violation of the integrity of the spinal column in the cervicothoracic region can lead to:

reflex spasm of the esophagus, difficulty swallowing and moving food

Damage to the middle chest segments, in addition to pain, can be accompanied by painful palpitations, nausea, vomiting, constipation and loose stools.

peptic ulcer of the stomach and duodenum. One of the reasons for the appearance of ulcerative defects is the hypersecretion of hydrochloric acid due to a violation of control by the central nervous system. Outgoing nerve impulses that regulate acid secretion are partially or completely blocked at the level of the affected segment.

inflammatory diseases of various parts of the gastrointestinal tract, liver, pancreas

pathology of the gallbladder associated with long-term spasm of sphincters and impaired bile flow. Over time, stagnation of bile and its natural "thickening" contribute to the sedimentation and adhesion of "hard particles" - stones appear.

References:

1. Rustamovich, A. I., Negmatovich, T. K., & Fazliddinovich, S. D. (2022). БОЛАЛИКДАН БОШ МИЯ ФАЛАЖИ ФОНИДА РИНОСИНУСИТИ БОР БЕМОРЛАРДА БУРУН БЎШЛИФИ МУКОЦИЛИАР ТРАНСПОРТИ НАЗОРАТИ ТЎҒРИСИДАГИ ЗАМОНАВИЙ ҚАРАШЛАР (адабиётлар шарҳи). JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE, 7(2).
2. Абдурахмонов, И. Р., & Шамсиев, Д. Ф. (2021). Эффективность применения местной антибиотикотерапии в лечении параназального синусита у детей с церебральным параличом. In НАУКА И ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ: СОХРАНЯЯ ПРОШЛОЕ, СОЗДАЁМ БУДУЩЕЕ (pp. 336-338).
3. Абдурахмонов, И. Р., & Шамсиев, Д. Ф. (2021). Болаликдан бош миё фалажи билан болалардаги ўтқир ва сурункали параназал синуситларни даволашда мукорегуляр дори воситасини самарадорлигини ўрганиш. Т [a_XW [i [S US S_^[ùe YfcS^, 58.
4. Siddikov, O., Daminova, L., Abdurakhmonov, I., Nuralieva, R., & Khaydarov, M. OPTIMIZATION OF THE USE OF ANTIBACTERIAL DRUGS DURING THE EXACERBATION OF CHRONIC OBSTRUCTIVE PULMONARY DISEASE. Turkish Journal of Physiotherapy and Rehabilitation, 32, 2.

5. Тураев, Х. Н. (2021). Абдурахмонов Илхом Рустамович Влияние будесонида на качество жизни пациентов с бронхиальным обструктивным синдромом. Вопросы науки и образования, 7, 132.
6. Абдурахманов, И., Шамсиев, Д., & Олимжонова, Ф. (2021). Изучение эффективности мукорегулярных препаратов в лечении острого и хронического параназального синусита при детском церебральном параличе. Журнал стоматологии и краниофациальных исследований, 2(2), 18-21.
7. Абдурахмонов, И. Р., & Шамсиев, Д. Ф. (2023). БОШ МИЯ ФАЛАЖИ ФОНИДАГИ ПАРАНАЗАЛ СИНУСИТЛАРНИ ДАВОЛАШДА ЎЗИГА ХОС ЁНДАШИШ. MedUnion, 2(1), 14-26.
8. Орипов, Р. А., Абдурахмонов, И. Р., Ахмедов, Ш. К., & Тураев, Х. Н. (2021). ОСОБЕННОСТИ ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ АНТИОКСИДАНТНЫХ ПРЕПАРАТОВ В ЛЕЧЕНИИ НЕЙРОДЕРМИТА.
9. Ахмедов, Ш. К., Тураев, Х. Н., Абдурахмонов, И. Р., & Орипов, Р. А. (2021). НЕКОТОРЫЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ТАКТИКИ ПРОДУКТИВНОГО ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ХРОНИЧЕСКОЙ КРАПИВНИЦЫ.
10. Абдурахмонов, И. Р. (2021). Исследование мукоцилиарной транспортной функции слизистой оболочки полости носа у больных с параназальным синуситом на фоне детского церебрального паралича. In Актуальные аспекты медицинской деятельности (pp. 256-259).
11. Абдурахмонов, И. Р., & Тураев, Х. Н. (2022). ОПЫТ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ СИНУПРЕТА С АНТИБАКТЕРИАЛЬНЫМИ ПРЕПАРАТАМИ В КОМПЛЕКСНОЙ ТЕРАПИИ РИНОСИНУСИТОВ У БОЛЬНЫХ ДЕТСКИМ ЦЕРЕБРАЛЬНЫМ ПАРАЛИЧОМ. Достижения науки и образования, (2 (82)), 88-92.
12. Abdurakhmanov, I., & Shernazarov, F. (2023). SPECIFIC ASPECTS OF TREATMENT OF CHRONIC RHINOSINUSITIS IN CHILDREN. Science and innovation, 2(D10), 164-168.
13. Andryev S. et al. Experience with the use of memantine in the treatment of cognitive disorders //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D11. – С. 282-288.
14. Antsiborov S. et al. Association of dopaminergic receptors of peripheral blood lymphocytes with a risk of developing antipsychotic extrapyramidal diseases //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D11. – С. 29-35.
15. Asanova R. et al. Features of the treatment of patients with mental disorders and cardiovascular pathology //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D12. – С. 545-550.
16. Begbudiyeв M. et al. Integration of psychiatric care into primary care //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D12. – С. 551-557.
17. Bo'Riyev B. et al. Features of clinical and psychopathological examination of young children //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D12. – С. 558-563.
18. Borisova Y. et al. Concomitant mental disorders and social functioning of adults with high-functioning autism/asperger syndrome //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D11. – С. 36-41.
19. Ivanovich U. A. et al. Efficacy and tolerance of pharmacotherapy with antidepressants in non-psychotic depressions in combination with chronic brain ischemia //Science and Innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 12. – С. 409-414.
20. Nikolaevich R. A. et al. Comparative effectiveness of treatment of somatoform diseases in psychotherapeutic practice //Science and Innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 12. – С. 898-903.

21. Novikov A. et al. Alcohol dependence and manifestation of autoaggressive behavior in patients of different types //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 413-419.
22. Pachulia Y. et al. Assessment of the effect of psychopathic disorders on the dynamics of withdrawal syndrome in synthetic cannabinoid addiction //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 240-244.
23. Pachulia Y. et al. Neurobiological indicators of clinical status and prognosis of therapeutic response in patients with paroxysmal schizophrenia //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 385-391.
24. Pogosov A. et al. Multidisciplinary approach to the rehabilitation of patients with somatized personality development //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 245-251.
25. Pogosov A. et al. Rational choice of pharmacotherapy for senile dementia //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 230-235.
26. Pogosov S. et al. Gnostic disorders and their compensation in neuropsychological syndrome of vascular cognitive disorders in old age //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 258-264.
27. Pogosov S. et al. Prevention of adolescent drug abuse and prevention of yatrogenia during prophylaxis //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 392-397.
28. Pogosov S. et al. Psychogenetic properties of drug patients as risk factors for the formation of addiction //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 186-191.
29. Prostyakova N. et al. Changes in the postpsychotic period after acute polymorphic disorder //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 356-360.
30. Prostyakova N. et al. Issues of professional ethics in the treatment and management of patients with late dementia //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 158-165.
31. Prostyakova N. et al. Sadness and loss reactions as a risk of forming a relationship together //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 252-257.
32. Prostyakova N. et al. Strategy for early diagnosis with cardiovascular diseaseisomatized mental disorders //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 166-172.
33. Rotanov A. et al. Comparative effectiveness of treatment of somatoform diseases in psychotherapeutic practice //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 267-272.
34. Rotanov A. et al. Diagnosis of depressive and suicidal spectrum disorders in students of a secondary special education institution //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 309-315.
35. Rotanov A. et al. Elderly epilepsy: neurophysiological aspects of non-psychotic mental disorders //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 192-197.